

Article

Homosexuality in India

Revisited: Some

Recommendations &

Research Directions

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Abstract

In the entire South Asian region, a history of toleration of same sex behavior between consenting adults had existed. It is only with the advent of criminalization of sodomy imposed by colonial powers, the notion of normal and abnormal sexual behaviors as dichotomized state became a reality in public discourse in India. Unfortunately, however, although Delhi High Court had decriminalized homosexuality in July 2009, it is still considered a taboo. Homophobia is prevalent across the nation!

Keywords: Homosexuality, Taboo, LGBT, Social Attitude

Introduction

Orientation of sexual activities or feeling towards others of the same sex exists in all cultures. Currently, most sociologists believe that one's sexual orientation –whether homosexual, heterosexual or something else – results from a complex interplay between biological factors and social learning (Giddens, 2008). Since *heterosexuality* is the norm for most people across the world, a great deal of research has focused on *why* some people become *homosexual*.

In his *The History of Sexuality*, Michel Foucault argues that the notion of the homosexual person seems barely to have existed during Victorian age. Sodomy was a category of forbidden acts. In England and several other European countries it was punishable by death (Foucault, 1978).

But it is to be remembered that sodomy was not defined as a homosexual offence. It was applied to relation between men and women, men and animals, as well as men among themselves. The term 'homosexuality' was coined in the 1860s, and from then on, homosexuals were increasingly regarded as being a separate type of people with a particular sexual aberration (Weeks, 1986).

It became part of a 'medicalized' discourse and was spoken of in clinical terms as a psychiatric disorder or a perversion, rather than a religious 'sin' (Giddens, 2008). As a result, homosexuality had come to be widely stigmatized. However, in the late 20th century, a number of investigations using psychological tests could not differentiate heterosexual from homosexual orientation. Research also demonstrated that people with homosexual orientation did not have any objective psychological dysfunction or impairments in judgment, stability and vocational capabilities (Rao, 2012). The American Psychiatric Association, in 1973ⁱ, and the World Health Organizationⁱⁱ, in 1992, officially accepted homosexuality as a normal variant of human sexuality. Unfortunately, although Delhi High Court had decriminalized homosexual intercourse between consenting adults in July 2009, it is still considered a taboo subject in Indian society. Homophobia is prevalent across the nation! The purpose of the present paper, however, is to focus on the context of the nature of same sex love in India and finding out future research directions. Before discussing the context let us clarify some relevant terms, concepts effectively for an in-depth understanding.

As it was previously mentioned, one's *sexual orientation* results from a complex interplay between biological factors and social

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learning. It is one of four components of sexuality and is distinguished by an emotional, romantic, sexual or affectionate attraction to individuals of a particular sex. The three other components are biological sex (whether we are born as a male or female), gender identity (the psychological sense of being male or female) and social gender role (the extent to which people conform to what is regarded in our society as feminine and masculine behaviour)ⁱⁱⁱ. Sexual orientation, however, also refers to a person's sense of identity based on those attractions, related behaviors, and membership in a community of others who share those attractions. Three sexual orientations are commonly recognized – heterosexual, homosexual (gay and lesbian) and bisexual. *Heterosexuality* involves the sexual or romantic attraction for persons of the opposite sex (*hetero* comes from the Greek word meaning 'other' or 'different'). Since heterosexuality is the norm for most people across the world, there is a common assumption that everyone is heterosexual or that lesbian, gay and bisexual orientations are a deviation from the 'heterosexual norm' (Allen, 2010) The assumption is called *heteronormativity*. Such assumption leads to the dislike of same-sex attraction and love or the hatred of people who have those feelings. As a result a sense of fear or prejudice and discrimination get arise among lesbian, gay and bisexual people in our society which has come to be referred as *homophobia* (Allen, 2010). The term was first used in the 1970s and is more associated with ignorance, prejudice and stereotyping than with the physiological reactions usually attributed to a 'phobia'. While homophobic comments or attitudes are often unintentional, they can cause hurt and offence to lesbian, gay and bisexual people. On the other hand, however, homosexuality involves the sexual or romantic attraction for persons of one's own sex. Today the term *gay* is used to refer to male homosexuals, *lesbian* for female homosexuals, and *bi* as shorthand for bisexual, people who experience sexual or romantic attraction for persons of either sex. Kenneth Plummer distinguished four types of homosexuality within modern Western culture. These are *Causal homosexuality* (homosexual encounter that does not substantially structure a person's overall sexual life), *situated activities* (circumstances in which homosexual acts are regularly carried out but

do not become an individual's overriding preference), *personalized homosexuality* (have a preference for homosexual activities but is isolated from groups in which this is easily accepted), and *Homosexuality as a way of life* (individuals who have 'come out' and have made associations with others of similar sexual tastes as a key part of their lives) (Giddens, 2008). Actually, open disclosure that one is lesbian, gay or bisexual is commonly referred to as '*coming out*'. However, there is more to coming out than disclosure of one's sexual orientation. Coming out is an important and affirmative developmental stage in the lives of lesbian, gay and bisexual people (Mayock, 2009). It involves accepting one's lesbian, gay or bisexual (LGB) orientation, choosing to share this information with others and developing a positive LGB identity. It is important to emphasize that coming out is process rather than a once-off event. Coming out does not mean you are choosing to be lesbian, gay or bisexual but rather that you are accepting that you are lesbian, gay or bisexual. While some people have negative experience when they come out, the majority of LGB people experience great relief when they come out and are increasingly met with support and acceptance from family and friends.

The heritage of toleration (?) to the history of decriminalization:

In shaping Indian customs and tradition religion has played a decisive role. In the religions texts central to Hinduism, the largest religion in India, homosexuality has not been explicitly mentioned. It (Hinduism) has taken various positions, ranging from positive to neutral or antagonistic. Rig-Veda, one of the four canonical sacred texts of Hinduism says *Vikriti Evam Prakriti* (what seems unnatural is also natural), which some scholars believe recognizes the cyclical constancy of homosexual /transsexual dimensions of human life, like all forms of universal diversities.^{iv} Historical literary evidence indicates that homosexuality has been prevalent across the Indian subcontinent throughout history, and that homosexuals were (when?) not necessarily considered inferior in any way^v. The ancient Indian treatise on statecraft, the *Arthashastra*, mentions a wide variety of non-vaginal

sexual practices which were sought to be punished with the lowest grade of fine. While homosexual intercourse was not sanctioned, it was treated a very minor offence, and several kinds of heterosexual intercourse were punished more severely.^{vi} The oldest codes of conduct that were proposed to be followed by a Hindu, the *Manusmriti*, does include mention of homosexual practices, but only as something to be regulated. Though homosexuality was considered a part of sexual practices, it was not always well accepted. These were punishments prescribed for homosexual behaviour. For instance, a verse in *Manu Smriti* (Chapter 8, Verse 370) referring to sexual relations between an older woman and a virgin (woman) reads "...a woman who pollutes a damsel (virgin) shall instantly have (her head) shaved or two fingers cut off, and be made to ride (through the town) on a donkey", suggesting a severe punishment. However, Verse 369 referring to sexual relations between two virgins suggests a relatively milder punishment – "...a damsel who pollutes (another) damsel must be fined two hundred (panas), pay the double of her (nuptial) fee, and receive ten (lashes with a) rod". These provisions, quoted out of context, seem against lesbianism, but in fact they are concerned not with the gender of the partners but with the loss of virginity that rendered a young woman unworthy of marriage. For instance, Verse 367, which refers to the punishment for forced sex act between a man and a woman, states, "...if any man through insolence forcibly contaminates a maiden, two of his fingers shall be instantly cut off, and he shall pay a fine of six hundred (panas)", which seems more severe in comparison to the punishment prescribed for the same act between two virgins. Sex between non-virgin women incurred a very small fine, while homosexual intercourse between men was sought to be censured by a prescription of a bath with one's clothes on, and a penance of "eating the five products of the cow and keeping a one-night fast"- the penance being a replacement of the traditional concept of homosexual intercourse resulting in a loss of caste^{vii}. The classic Indian text *Kama Sutra* deals without ambiguity or hypocrisy with all aspects of sexual life—including marriage, adultery, prostitution, group sex, sadomasochism, male and female homosexuality, and transvestism^{viii}.

Homosexual intercourse was, however, a criminal offence until 2009 under section 377 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860. This made it an offence for a person to voluntarily have "carnal intercourse against the order of nature". The section was authored by Lord Macaulay, the President of the Indian Law Commission, as part of Britain's efforts to impose Victorian values on its biggest colony (similar laws were imposed on most of its colonies, including the United States) (Misra, 2009) It reads as follows:

"Section 377 : Unnatural offences-whoever voluntarily has carnal intercourse against the order of nature with any man, woman or animal shall be punished with imprisonment for life ,or with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to 10 years, and shall be liable to fine. Explanation- penetration is sufficient to constitute the carnal intercourse necessary to the offence described in this section (IPC: 2009)"

Although not explicitly defined, "carnal intercourse against the order of nature" has been taken by the Indian courts in the intervening years to include anal sex, oral sex, and in some cases other non-procreative sexual acts, such as mutual masturbation (Gupta, 2006). Although heterosexual couples also partake in these acts, the weight of the law over the centuries has fallen on homosexual sex. Even when such sex is consensual, the "voluntary" provision in the law makes it illegal. However, although few cases against consenting adults have gone to trial, the existence of Section 377, and the threat of possible arrest, have allowed the authorities to discriminate against homosexuals and organizations working with them. Thus, Section 377 has had an enormous negative impact on many people's lives.

A number of incidents have highlighted the vulnerability of gay, lesbian and transgender Indians as a result of Section 377. Homosexually inclined men who meet in parks and other public places are often entrapped and blackmailed by the police, who use the threat of penalty under Section 377 against them. In December 1999, the film 'Fire' was released in India's major

cities. This was the first Hindi film dealing largely with a lesbian relationship. Although it was passed by the National Film Censor Board, thugs supporting the Hindu fundamentalist group Shiv Sena reacted by vandalizing cinemas, attacking movie-goers, and demanding, in vain, that the film be banned (Ramasubban, 2008). Many non-governmental organizations working with individuals marginalized by their sexuality have also been harassed. In 2002 in Bangalore, Sangama, a non-governmental organization working with sexuality minorities, was the victim of

sustained repression as the police barred people seeking their services from visiting its offices and ordered it to hold meetings with them outside the city (Ramasubban, 2008). And in 2001 four activists from Bharosa Trust and Naz Foundation International, organizations working on HIV/AIDS in Lucknow, were accused of running a gay “sex club” and charged under Section 377. The activists, whose employers were recognized by the state AIDS control agency, had been distributing condoms and educational pamphlets to gay men. They were released after 47 days in custody following nationwide protests (Gupta, 2006).

It was in response to the 1994 Delhi prison case that an initial suit was filed against Section 377 in the Delhi High Court in 1994. ABVA (AIDS Bhedbhawe Virodhi Andolon), a Delhi based NGO, filed public interest litigation calling for the repeal of Section 377 on the grounds that it violated the constitutional right to privacy. The next attempt to repeal Section 377 began in 2001. The Naz Foundation India Trust, based in Delhi, whose workers had suffered police harassment during HIV education campaigns among marginalized communities, joined up with the Lawyers Collective, a legal aid organization working for the rights of people affected by HIV and AIDS. They petitioned the Delhi High Court not to repeal Section 377 as a whole, but to read it down to exclude private consensual sex between adults. The petition challenged Section 377's violation of four fundamental rights guaranteed by the Indian Constitution: the right to equality before the law (Article 14), since Section 377 discriminates against particular groups; the right to be free from sex

discrimination (Article 15), since the law primarily targets homosexual sex; the right to fundamental liberties (Article 19); and the right to life and privacy (Article 21), since Section 377 imperils lives by impeding HIV prevention activities and intrudes upon the private consensual sex of adults (Misra, 2009). By 2009, however, the political and social climate had shifted so much that human rights had become a key part of the petition. At last, on July 2009, two judges of Delhi High Court ruled that consensual sex between same-sex adults is legal. With this, an eight-year advocacy campaign was brought to a successful conclusion.

Homosexual identity & the prevalence of homophobia: the Indian experience

In India, issues related to sexuality and sexual behaviours have for a long time been seen through the lens of western framework. But, it does not suggest that these frameworks are invalid! Rather, the tendency to deny the existence of diverse sexualities within South Asia, both by various Western discourses and discourses of South Asian origin have had a central impact on understanding of South Asian sexualities and gender identities in general and Indian in particular (Shah, 2007). Sexual and gender identities/orientations take shape within psychosocial and historical processes, which in turn are contextualized by culture and language. Therefore, one may find that different cultures often translate similar words and phenomena into different meanings with inherent subtleties typical of that culture (Khan, 2006). It is, therefore, clear that Eurocentric perceptions and values give a definition to heterosexual, homosexual and bisexual identities quite different from how these phenomena are understood in India. In India, sexuality or sexual identity is primarily defined within frameworks of gender roles/orientation and reproductive sex, rather than in sexual orientation. Sexual interaction between LGBT people is also defined by the gender/sex role that each partner plays. Thus the penetrating partner perceives himself as a man penetrating a ‘not-man’. This fact, however, also underlines a history of tolerance of same sex behaviours between consenting

adults that has existed in the entire South Asian region. It is only with the advent of criminalization of sodomy imposed by the colonial powers, which the notion of right and wrong, and normal and abnormal sexual behaviors as dichotomized state became a reality in public discourse. And this discourse has taken shape in the gendered context of South Asia (Khan, 2006).

However, there is no available evidence that provides a reliable estimate of the numbers of LGBT people in India. There exist a good deal of small scale qualitative research that explores the experiences of LGBT people in public life, but the detailing of actual size of the population is absent. Reasons for this lack of evidence are debatable and varied. Betts, (2008), for example, suggested that when people are asked to define their sexual orientation (or gender), there is a generalized failure to capture the subtlety that may be associated with varying definitions and categorization of sexual minorities. Most studies, however, carried out in Western countries, report a wide range –anything between 2 per cent and 13per cent of the population exhibits same sex preference. In India, the National Aids Control Organization Expert Groups says that there are 25 lakh males having sex with males.^{ix} But if the most conservative western estimate of 2per cent is taken, and extrapolated on the Indian population in the assumption that gayness is universal, the Indian homosexual community-including men and women-would at least be over 20 million strong. At the upper end of 13per cent, it would be large as the country's largest minority community!

Homophobia remains rampant across India despite the 2009 court ruling overturning a colonial law declaring homosexuality to be a crime punishable by 10 years in jail. A recent countrywide survey by the CNN-IBN television news channel revealed that as many as 73 per cent of Indians believe homosexuality should be illegal. The poll, which was conducted in urban neighbourhoods, showed that 83 per cent of respondents felt that homosexuality was not part of Indian culture whilst 90 per cent said they would not rent their houses to a gay or lesbian couple. The majority of Indian homosexuals – many of whom still live with the

parents – refer to their partners as “friends” for fear of being disowned by their families. Many are forcibly married off, trapped in a cycle of pretence and deception and facing social ridicule if they attempted to come out. And those who can live together do not advertise their sexuality, for fear of being evicted by landlords or preyed upon by the corrupt police who extort money from them on threat of exposure. Over the past decade there have been several press reports of lesbian and gay couples exchanging marriage vows, but these stories invariably excite crude humor. More recently hundreds of homosexuals from both sexes have attended pride parades in Delhi and Bangalore to lobby their cause. In one march men wore sparkling saris, women sported rainbow boas and hundreds of people chanted for gay rights on a short walk through Delhi's centre. But fear of ostracism was evident amongst many marchers who preferred to wear masks to conceal their identity. Even mainstream political and religious groups vehemently oppose homosexuality. Former MP B. P. Singhal from India's main Opposition Hindu nationalist Bharatiya Janata Party believes homosexuality to be an “evil exported from the West” - a view echoed by many other parliamentarians. And Father Dominic Emanuel of India's Catholic Bishop Council reacted angrily when the legal ban on gays was lifted saying that the church did not “approve” of homosexual behaviour as it did not consider it “natural, ethical or moral”.^x In 2003, Naz Foundation International (NFI) conducted a study to address the legal, social and judicial impediments for the improvement of the sexual health for males who have sex with males. Six cities were included in the study: Chennai, Hyderabad, Kolkata, Lucknow and Pune in India, and Dhaka in Bangladesh. According to the study, 75per cent of the respondents reported sexual assault as rape by policemen or goondas. Extortion, public harassment as violence like the threat of imprisonment, prolonged blackmail, beatings, restriction of movement in public places at the hands of police have also been reported by 70per cent of the total respondents. Furthermore 50per cent of the respondents stated that their fellow students or teachers had harassed them in school or colleges and 25per cent have sexually been abused by their own friends. The most unfortunate thing was that 28per

cent of the total respondents either thought of or tried to commit suicide at same point in their lives (Khan, 2006).

India, however, has a long history of women's subjugation. In such a sexually-repressive society where even straight women know sexuality most intimately through violence and not pleasure, where even heterosexual couples across the country are hacked to death for transgressing caste barriers, single mothers have no legal rights whatsoever, the plight of the lesbian can only be imagined. In our country, lesbian don't have access to public spaces where they (unlike gay/bisexual men) can meet other lesbians. School is one of the most powerful institutions of maintaining heteronormativity. It is also place where most adolescent lesbians realize their queerness. But, unfortunately it does not allow any space for alternative ideas. In 1992, seven students at a government high school for girls in Thiruvananthapuram formed a club to celebrate their lesbian status. The punishments that followed were remarkably severe- complete expulsion^{xi}. In the community, violence ranges from queer-bashing to losing jobs, residence etc. In 2001 a lesbian couple of Malda district was asked to leave their house since their presence was bad for the morals of the resident building. Again, Manisha and Tarana, a lesbian couple used to work in a leather factory, were sent back to their respective families in U.P in different trains. The family, hitherto considered the safest haven for all individuals is the important space of violence of the rights of queer people in India. Because, it is primarily based on heterosexist ethos. And, therefore, only heterosexual couples enjoy all socio-economic and legal benefits. *Humjinsi*, a resource book on queer rights, documents over 30 cases of lesbian couple committing suicide in a period of five years (Fernandez, 1999) According to Vasudevan^{xii}, a lesbian rights activist from Kerala, most women committing suicides are from Dalit, Adivasi, working class communities, and have therefore been subjected to multiple discriminations. Furthermore, most of the reported lesbian suicides happen in small towns and rural areas. Gay men can leave for urban centers and live in anonymity, but not many girls have the social, educational and material resources to migrate to an urban centre.

Conclusion: Recommendations and Research Directions

Recognizing the nature of the problem is one thing, finding solutions for the same is quite another. While it is clear that LGBT people in India still face severe discrimination from society, law and all other heteropatriarchal institutions, the sphere of discrimination is visible at both sides-public as well as private. Therefore challenging homophobia and transphobia as complex and multi-dimensional processes requires us to think differently about gender and sexual orientation and about how social institutions are structured. There is no short cut solution that can address the marginalization and homophobia facing many LGBT people in Indian society. Therefore, in the light of the above mentioned discussion, following recommendation can be developed in recognizing the role that individuals as well as institution can take effectively.

- 1) To change societal attitude media has to play a responsible role by reporting on LGBT issues and promoting a culture of tolerance and freedom for minorities.
- 2) Many people in India remain ignorant of and indifferent to section 377, or unable to access justice where they are aware of their rights. So efforts will need to be made to ensure that it is implemented at the local level and among marginalized communities.
- 3) Police force at all level needs to be sensitized on LGBT issues and also on the general principles of fundamental human rights.
- 4) Legal funds need to be created that can take on Public Interest Litigation on LGBT issues.
- 5) Training needs to be conducted for health professionals (doctors and nurses) to increase their understanding of LGBT identity as potential risk factor for self-harm suicidal behavior and depression.
- 6) Respective authorities should ensure that health, mental health and social care services are provided in a way that is accessible and appropriate to LGBT people.

- 7) Schools are one of the key arena within which heterosexual identities are constructed as 'normal', while LGBT identities are constructed as pathological. Schools and teacher education programmes are therefore crucial sites where LGBT issues and concerns need to be addressed.
- 8) The department of health and family welfare should develop a resource and information pack and make it accessible to the parents and family members of LGBT people.
- 9) The department of youth affairs should ensure that all policies it develops are fully inclusive of the needs of LGBT young people.
- 10) National as well as state government should develop initiatives to support employers in making workplace and workplace culture more supportive and inclusive of LGBT people.
- 11) To check the violence that is perpetrated in the home as well as in the public sphere, the domestic violence law has to be expanded to include non-spousal and parental violence as well.

A notable feature of Indian social research is that there are very few effective studies that address sexuality of LGBT people as a lived reality (Chandiramani, 2010). Less efforts have been made to differentiate behavior, identity and desire. It has also been found that the given attentions of same sex relations are gender-biased, geared almost entirely to men. Researchers did not show their interest to lesbians or lesbian relation. Few groups (for example- men who have sex with men) got special attention because of their vulnerability to HIV. Therefore, LGBT- specific topics where research (including qualitative, quantitative and mixed-methods research) is urgently required include:

1. LGBT youth development and identity, with particular attention to the coming out process.
2. LGBT youth and schooling.
3. Older LGBT people, and

4. LGBT families and parenting.

Glossary of terms

LGBT: acronym for lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender.

Transphobia: a fear, dislike or hatred of people who are transgender, transsexual or challenge conventional gender categories of male/ female.

Notes

ⁱ American Psychological Association (2008). *"Answers to your questions: for a better understanding of sexual orientation and homosexuality"*. Retrieved from

www.apa.org/topics/sexuality/orientation.pdf

ⁱⁱ World Health Organization. (2005). *"Promoting Mental Health: concepts, emerging evidence, practice"*. Geneva: WHO. Retrieved from http://www.who.int/topics/mental_health/en/

ⁱⁱⁱ American Psychological Association, loc.cit.

^{iv} Wikipedia. (2012). *"Homosexuality in India"*. Retrieved from

<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HomosexualityinIndia>

^vVanita, R. & Kidwai, S. (2001). *Same-Sex Love in India: Readings from Literature and History*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

^{vi} Ibid p.25.

^{vii} Ibid

^{viii} Wikipedia. (2012). "*Homosexuality in India*". Retrieved from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Homosexuality_in_India

^{ix} Times News Network. (2009, July 3). "*Gay count varies from 2% to 13% of population*". The Times Of India. Retrieved from <http://articles.timesofindia.indiatimes.com>

^x Telegraph News Network. (2013, January 6). "*Homophobia persists in India despite court reforms*". The Telegraph. Retrieved from <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/asia/india/8618084>

^{xi} Khaitan, T.(2004). "*Violence against lesbians in India*". Retrieved from <http://www.attlawforum.org/Resources/lexlib/document.2004-12-21.95556965551>

^{xii} Ibid.

^{xii} Vasudevan, D. "*Lesbian Suicides and the Kerala Women's Movement*". Paper presented at South Indian Young Feminist's Conference, September 29, 2001.

References

Allen, O. (2010). *Gay, Lesbian and Bisexual People: A Good Practice for Mental Health Nurses*. Dublin: GLEN.

Betts, P. (2008). *Developing Questions on Sexuality Identity: UK experiences of administering survey questions on sexual identity/orientation*. London: Office for National Statistics.

Chandiramani, R. K. (2010). *Sexuality and Sexual Behaviour*. New Delhi: CREA.

Fernandez, B. (1999). *Humjinsi: A resource book on lesbian, gay and bisexual rights in India*. Mumbai: Centre for Human Rights and Law.

Foucault, M. (1978). *The History of Sexuality*. London: Penguin.

Giddens, A. (2008). *Sociology*. New Delhi: WILEY-INDIA.

Gupta, A. (2006). "Section 377 and the dignity of Indian homosexuals". *Economic and Political Weekly* , 27-34.

Khan, S. &. (2006). *From the frontline: A report of a study into the impact of social, legal and judicial impediments to sexual health promotion, care and support for males who have sex with males in Bangladesh and India* . Lucknow: Naz Foundation.

Mayock, P. (2009). *Supporting LGBT lives: a study of the mental health and well-being of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people*. Dublin: GLEN.

Misra, G. (2009). "Decriminalising homosexuality in India". *Reproductive Health Matter* , PP. 20-28.

Rao, T. &. (2012). "Homosexuality and India". *Indian Journal of Psychiatry* , pp.1-3.

Ramasubban, R. (2008). Political intersections between HIV/AIDS, sexuality and human rights: a history of resistance to the anti-sodomy law in India. *Global Public Health* , 22-28.

Shah, V. &. (2007). *My Body is not Mine: Stories of violence and tales of hope*. New Delhi: Naz Foundation International.

Weeks, J. (1986). *Sexuality*. London: Methuen.